

AN EXPOSITION OF THE ETHICAL IMPLICATION OF MIND-BODY DUALISM ON SOCIAL VICES IN NIGERIAN EDUCATIONAL SECTOR.

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Abstract

Mind-body dualism is a philosophical thesis that postulates the ontological existences of two independent substances. This philosophical disposition has far-reaching ethical implication on social vices and holistic education. Holistic education demands the balancing of the physical and non-physical aspect of the learner. However, in contemporary Nigerian educational sector, it is becoming increasingly common to observe the imbalances in physical and non-physical well-being of learners. This study exposes the ethical implication of over-emphasising one ontological aspect over and above the other. The study is qualitative in nature due to the primary focus on library sources. Being philosophical, the study adopts descriptive and speculative methods. The study found out that prevalence of social vices such as examination malpractice and indecent dressing in schools are largely due to ontological imbalances in mind-body relationship. This study revealed that, better understanding of the relationship between physical and non-physical aspect of the learner is critical in fighting social vices in Nigerian educational sector. The paper concluded that the Nigerian educational sector will be transformed and more productive if such ethical implications are stressed.

Key Words: Mind, Body, Dualism, Social vices, Education

Introduction

Social vices such as examination malpractice, drug abuse, indecent dressing, cultism, sexual promiscuity, religious fanaticisms among others are common in Nigerian educational sector. It

appears perpetrators of such vices are unaware of the physical and non-physical causes and consequences. The prevalence of these social vices in Nigerian educational sector is alarming. This study discusses the imbalances of mind-body relationship as one of the factors responsible for this alarming rate of social vices in educational sector.

In philosophy, the ontology of a human person according to Rene Descartes (1596–1650) comprises of the mind and body as independent substances. This philosophical doctrine is known as substance dualism (Modak 2017, Lennon 2017, Uchenna 2025). One of the most challenging task of a human person is to balance these two distinct and sometimes opposing substances. This challenge has resulted to several imbalances in human relationship particularly in educational institutions.

This study asserts that, promotion of substance dualism in Nigerian educational sector will deliberately expose learners and educational stakeholders to an appreciation of the relationship between social vices and the ontology of a human person. Furthermore, promotion of substance dualism could enhance discovery of self, improvement of self-esteem, critical thinking, creativity, innovation, and invention.

Mind-Body Dualism

Mind-body dualism or Substance dualism is a philosophical thesis which present the mind and the body as distinct kind of entities. The body is made up of a physical substance, whereas the mind is something more like a ghostly soul, which is non-physical (Modak 2017). In other words, substance dualism present physical and non-physical aspects of our existence as distinct kind of entities.

This view in modern philosophy is associated with Rene Descartes (1596–1650), who was a French mathematician, Philosopher, and Scientist of the 17th century. Descartes argued to the conclusion that reality consists of two distinct substances: *res cogitans* and *res extensa*. i.e, the thinking substance, or mind and the extended substance, or body (Uchenna 2025). Descartes maintained that the mind, being non-material and rational, is separate from the body, which is mechanical and operates under natural laws.

Descartes' in his "*Meditations*," established a clear explanation of the difference between the non-physical and the physical attributes of a human person, arguing that the body functions as a mechanical entity governed by natural laws, while the mind is free from such constraints (Uchenna, 2025). Substantiating Descartes argument, Modak (2017) notes that the human mind is

a separate entity from the body due to its immortal nature and free will to decide. This justified the non-physical nature of the human mind which is not extended. By extension here, we implied the inability to measure the human mind in terms of shape, size, height, length and width. The human mind does not possess such attributes.

The human body is mortal and mechanical. i.e, it is extended and defined by the laws of nature. It has shape, height, and size among many extended attributes. The ontological existence of extended and non-extended features of man are important in his interaction and understanding of social vices. However, relationship of the two substance is still debatable. It is worthy to note that, the two independent substances relate but need to be balance so as to avoid overlap.

Accordingly, Modak (2017) explained that, in the dualist approach, the mind is metaphysical and private substance while the body is physical and public. As noted earlier, Descartes maintained that the mind, being non-physical and rational, is not the same with the body. This dualistic disposition laid the foundation for debates on human consciousness, identity, and morality. Descartes perspective on the nature of a human person has shaped the understanding of morality for centuries.

Basically, philosophers of the mind and education have been interested in understanding the ontology of the human mind. However, our concern is epistemological and ethical in nature. Epistemological quest is beyond the ontological structures of the mind but the possibility of distinguishing one's mind and the mind of others. In other words, is our mental state or that of the other knowable? (Modak 2017). Do students and teachers usually understand and appreciate the distinction between the mind and the body? The answer to these questions have far-reaching ethical implications on educational norms and social vices in our schools. It defines how we conduct examination, engage in sexual relationship and seek financial rewards.

Despite the importance of mind-body dualism, it has been variously criticized particularly by feminist theorist who highlights its limitations in addressing the complexities of corporeality and identity. Feminist theorist argued that the rigid separation of mind and body by substance dualist often leads to an undervaluation of bodily experiences and promotion of corporeal existence (Uchenna 2025). Consequently depict women as inferior beings.

Education

It is a difficult task to define education due to diverse conceptualisation by scholars. Education means different things in different contexts: to some, it is the idea of being an institution, a

discipline, a product, a process or counselling et al. The conceptualization of education varies from society to society. What is considered as education depends on societal needs (Igboabuchi and Ofojebe 2010).

For instance, societies that are monastically inclined are likely to define education with high regards to religiosity and spirituality. While societies that are technologically inclined are likely to emphasize the advancement of scientific knowledge in its conceptualization of education. However, this kind of educational philosophy is a potential hindrance to holistic education as it emphasizes the development of one ontological aspect (mind/body) at the expense of the other.

Consequently, defining education is tasking given its relative and evolutionary nature. However, for the purpose of this study, the following definitions are selected for an exposition of ethical implications of mind-body dualism on social vices in Nigerian educational sector. One of the earliest attempts to define education was by Plato as quoted in Igboabuchi and Ofojebe (2010). Plato asserts that “By education, I mean that training which is given by suitable habits to the first instincts of virtue in children, when pleasure and pain are rightly implanted in non-rational souls. The particular training in respect of pleasure and pain ...is called education”. This definition by Plato is dualistic in nature due to its recognition of pleasure and pain as separate entities. However, Plato’s definition does not take into cognizance the training of the body but overemphasized the right implantation of pleasure and pain in a non-rational soul (child).

According to Dewey (1957) “education is the process of forming fundamental dispositions, and emotions towards nature and fellow men or the basic process of creating a natural, intellectual, emotional reaction towards nature and mankind. He also further emphasizes that education is the way of using knowledge to help mankind to acquire more knowledge which will ultimately lead to a more harmonious, productive, meaningful and elevated existence in the end”.

Cole (2018) defined education as a method or practice that aims at teaching an individual a new skill or new principles. According to Adesemowo and Sotonade (2022), it is the act or process of educating or applying discipline on the mind or a process of character training. Winters (2009) defined education as the acquisition of knowledge. She viewed it as taking ownership of the information given to you whether through formal education or through life skills.

In Nigeria, the formal education sector has been grappling with a lot of social vices. Such vices include; examination malpractice, indecent dressing, cultism, cyber-crimes, corruption, drugs abuse and extortion among others. These social vices can be best assessed by re-evaluating the

philosophical orientations which ought to act as the substructure of the educational policy and goals of the nation. Philosophical orientation such as mind-body dualism which stresses the importance of understanding the relationship between the physical and non-physical aspect of our existence should be inculcated and promoted in schools.

Social Vices

Social vices as noted by Sekh et al (2023) are “practices, behaviors or habits generally considered immoral, sinful, rude, taboo, and criminal or degrading in the associated society”. These are visible in all institutions of the society. They are manifested in political, religious, educational and economic terms. The institutions of the society are both causative and curative agents of social vices.

Ariyo (2017) asserts that social vices are “extremely bad immoral behaviors that constitute a nuisance to the society”. Defining social vices as ‘extremely bad immoral behavior questions the classification of those immoral behaviors that are not extremely bad as to whether they are virtues and moral. Social vices are immoral behaviors, little or extreme. Misrepresentation of concepts such as social vices limits efforts of eliminating them in the society.

According to Jointheir (2016) social vices are “forms of immoral, criminal, and wicked behaviors in the people”. Actions that contradict rules and values are vices and are social when it has to relate with the other. Such actions are often negative behaviors. Contextually, social vices are actions that contradict educational rules and values. Generally, examples of social vices include prostitution, indecent dressing, rape, drug abuse, hooliganism, lesbianism, sodomy, alcoholism, incest, pedophilia, rape, kidnapping, smoking, pre-marital sexual activities, examination malpractice, terrorism, political thuggery, gambling, pocket picking, robbery, electoral malpractices, child abuse, cultism, corruption, bribery, domestic violence, internet crimes among others. It is worthy to note that not all of the above are applicable to educational institutions.

Methodology of the Study

This study utilises descriptive and speculative philosophical methods using library based secondary sources. Mbachirin (2019) notes that descriptive method “helps to obtain information concerning the current status of a thing...” Speculative methods helps to enquire into the nature of an order of reality and applied it not just to a particular reality or experience, but to all knowledge and all experiences seeing it as a whole (Chukwuokolo 2021). These methods are critical in

exposing the ethical implication of mind-body dualism on social vices in Nigerian educational sector.

Social Vices in Nigerian Educational Sector and the Implications of Mind-Body Dualism

In many Nigerian schools today, there seems to be rising tide in the imbalance between the physical and non-physical inclination of learners and stakeholders. This imbalances are responsive for social vices involving teachers, learners, and other stakeholders in the educational sector. For instance, Apologun (2001) observed that “cases of examination malpractice, sexual harassment, cultism, extortion, compromising of standards and integrity, etc, involving lecturers, teachers, and staff of schools have become prevalent in our educational system”.

Consequently, our focus is on examination malpractice, indecent dressing, drugs abuse, cultism, and religious fanaticism as forms of social vices in Nigerian educational sector. We argued that the prevalence of these social vices is due to imbalances in mind-body relationship which result to high inclination to either physical or non-physical gratification.

Examination Malpractice: Hiko (2008) notes that “examination malpractice is an unlawful or intolerable behavior by someone who break the examination rules at the time knowledge is being tested”. Basically, the philosophical underpinning of the issue of examination malpractice encompasses not only epistemological but metaphysical, ethical, logical and aesthetical concerns. During examination, both the physical and non-physical aspects of participants are tested. Philosophers seek to know the reasons for examination malpractice, how it is conducted and the consequences thereof. Our objective is to expose the physical or non-physical causes and consequences of examination malpractice.

Oko (2016) in his studies on ‘Examination Malpractice: Causes, Effects and Possible Ways of Curbing the Menace. A Study of Cross River State University of Technology’ revealed an array of factors responsible for examination malpractice in Nigeria to includes “wrong value system which leads to serious quest for certification instead of knowledge and skills, Laziness, lack of preparation or in-adequate preparation for examination, lack of self-confidence, poor school facilities, (Lack of or in-adequate examination hall) poor sitting arrangement, socio-economic factors, political- undertone, privatization and commercialization of education, poor invigilation, weak parental function et al”.

This clearly demonstrate a mixture of physical and non-physical causes thereby substantiating our argument for a need to balance both the physical needs and non-physical demands. Examination

participant and educational institutions must understand that examination does not constitute only physical arrangement but non-physical preparation as well. We can only fight examination malpractice when the body and the mind are adequately taken care of. Overemphasis on any of these distinct but unrelated ontological substances will only fuel the social vice of examination malpractice in our educational sector.

Educational establishments must recognize that physical arrangement such as adequate examination hall, good sitting arrangement and invigilation are not enough to eliminate examination malpractice in our schools. Physical preparation must agree with non-physical prerequisite of examination practices such self-confidence, and good value system et'al. Students must understand that prayer alone is not a guarantee for examination malpractice free educational system.

Indecent Dressing: indecent dressing is another social vice in Nigerian educational sector that illicit our interest. Fayokun et al (2009) assert that indecent dressing among youths especially on the universities campuses has forced the authorities to enact dress codes to stem the tide and restore high moral standards, integrity and decency. Many educational institutions has dress code, yet the scorch has continue to spread among learners in Nigerian schools like wildfire.

Dualist philosophers especially advocates of substances dualism are concerned about the impact of indecent dressing on mind-body relationship. They attempt to understand if indecent dressing has impact on both the physical and non-physical aspects of learners. If the old adage which say 'you are address the way you dress' is true, then the dualist position is worthy reflection.

In Nigeria, dress codes are very important recognizing identity. Dressing can be used to identify one's profession, ethnicity, behavioral mood and character trait among others. It is germane to find out why indecent dressing persist despite the importance of decent dressing codes in the society. Fayokun et al (2009) identified absence of procedural and legal structures for enforcement and sanctions of indecent dressing, weak moral backgrounds and lip-service paid to the issue of dress code by the authorities as well as negative influence of foreign cultures through the moral pollution of the mass media among others. In addition, the societal eugenic and aesthetical inclination to the physical over and above the non-physical has contributed greatly in promoting indecent dressing in Nigerian educational sector.

Drug Abuse: This is also called substance abuse. This is the continued misuse of drugs. It is an illness that is considered by a destructive outline of consuming a substance that leads to noteworthy

problems or suffering (Sekh et al 2023). National Institute on drug Abuse (2003) describe drug abuse as the habit of illegal drugs and misuse of legal drugs. Hassan (2019) identified marijuana, alcohol, codeine, cannabis, cocaine, inhalants, stimulants, hallucinogens, sedatives and narcotics as common drugs that are abused. He notes the consequences to include “poor academic performance, criminality, mental disorder, violence, family problem/disharmony, low self-esteem, physical injury and death”.

Drug abuse is a social vice that demands the attention of all stakeholders in educational sector particularly due to its prevalence on campuses across the country. Understanding philosophical dualism is critical in the fight against drug abuse among students. There is a need to understand the physical and non-physical causes and consequences of drug abuse. This will help formulating effective policies in the fight against drug abuse.

Religious Fanaticism: This is one of the social vices in educational sector that clearly demonstrate the imbalances in the physical and non-physical aspect of learners. Religious fanaticism is “an irrational attitude to religion which leads the religionist to the practice of religion beyond the bounds of reason and, therefore, without moderation” (Iwe 2000). Religious fanaticism has also been described as “the blind belief that an idea or doctrine is absolutely true, and that it is acceptable or even right to force others to share that particular idea” (Gwamna 2014). Onimhwo and Ottuh (2007) stated that to become a religious fanatic is to be wild and excessive about matters that relate to one’s belief. This attitude is caused by imbalances in mind-body relationship which define high inclination to spiritual gratification. Often caused by poor spiritual leadership.

This is a social vice affecting students and teachers. Religious fanaticism has affected the relationship between students and teacher. Some students think education is the non-physical matter thereby spending good time in prayers without much attention to physical aspect of their studies. Some are prayer worriers, praying and expecting miraculous distinction in their courses. This is a clear demonstration of imbalances in the body-mind relationship.

Conclusion

Mind-body dualism as postulated in Cartesian philosophy has greatly influence the understanding of social vices and educational policies. Rene Descartes dualistic philosophy is critical in understanding practical educational issues such as examination malpractice, indecent dressing, religious fanaticism, and drug abuse. Many social vices in educational institution can be link to the imbalances in mind-body relationship. The human person is in a constant search to balance the

physical and the non-physical aspect of his being. Therefore, it is important to incorporate substance dualism in navigating the spaces of social vices in our schools. Recognizing this philosophical disposition will help in the formulation of sound educational policies and alleviation of social vices.

Recommendations.

Sequel to the above discussion, the following under listed are recommended:

- i. Examination is beyond pen and paper, conducive halls and good sitting arrangement. It involves the critical non-physical aspect of the learner and examination stakeholders. Therefore, adequate physical and non-physical preparation should be provided as a way of balancing the human ontology and reducing examination malpractice.
- ii. Fight against indecent dressing should incorporate non-physical effort towards value orientation. This will contribute significantly in balancing the two distinct human ontologies.
- iii. There is every need to de-emphasis the possibility of miracle result so as to encourage physical effort. This will help in balancing the physical and non-physical effort of learners and teachers.

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